

Abattoir Users Survey 2025

**Sustainable
Food Trust**

RBST

Rare Breeds Survival Trust

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Executive Summary

The 2025 Abattoir Users Survey was carried out by the Sustainable Food Trust, Soil Association and Rare Breeds Survival Trust to better understand the importance of small abattoirs for farming and meat businesses.

Small abattoirs continue to close across the UK, posing a severe threat to the future of local meat supply.

With 850 responses from farmers and land managers across the UK, the findings outlined below reflect respondents' views on the key role small and local abattoir services play in supporting:

Stronger, more resilient local meat supply chains, supporting national food security and helping to satisfy consumers' increasing interest in meat provenance and sustainability.

Rural economic growth, supporting farm businesses and jobs in livestock husbandry, slaughter, butchery, retail and agritourism.

Public goods delivery, by improving the viability of farmers already practising, or shifting towards, sustainable livestock production.

Conservation of rare and native breeds which are important for genetic diversity and semi-natural habitat management, including rewilding projects.

Improved animal welfare, for example through enabling reduced journey times to slaughter and supporting high-welfare farming systems.

Key Findings

Economic growth

- 58% of respondents believed their business would not be profitable without selling direct to consumers or through local markets – a model which depends heavily on private kill and further processing services offered by small and local abattoirs.
- 61% have seen increased demand for their meat products in recent years, yet meeting this demand is a challenge due to limited access to suitable abattoir services. A third have seen their local abattoir close in the last five years, while a quarter report their abattoir is too busy or fully booked – often as a result of nearby closures.
- With better access to a local abattoir, almost 25% said they could expand their business, while 17% could diversify.

Local food and rural communities

- 60% of respondents sell their meat direct to local consumers and 30% supply local businesses.
- However, due to abattoir closures or limited access to services, many farmers have had to send livestock to market or large processors instead of processing for local sale.
- If their current abattoir closed, 43% said they would no longer sell meat locally and 29% would have to close their business.
- If access to a local abattoir improved, 27% said they could sell meat locally and 10% could employ more staff.

Public goods

- 83% of respondents said livestock play an important role in delivering public goods on their farm – particularly in habitat creation and conservation, as well as enhancing overall farm sustainability (e.g. improved soil health, pest and weed management and reducing reliance on agrochemicals).
- 77% keep native breeds, including 37 breeds listed as 'Priority' or 'At Risk' by the Rare Breeds Survival Trust.
- If their abattoir were to close, 17% said they would no longer keep native breeds.

Animal welfare

- Nearly 60% of respondents travel less than 30 miles to their abattoir, yet a significant number face much longer journeys, with 10% travelling over 60 miles.
- Respondents consistently raised concerns about the animal welfare implications of long-distance transport (typically beyond 30–40 miles) and the need to send animals to market unnecessarily. Many felt this undermines their high on-farm welfare standards – a consequence of limited access to local slaughter facilities.

Recommendations

The following recommendations outline how national and local governments, regulators, industry and producers can take coordinated action to secure the future of the small abattoir sector:

1 National Government should formally recognise the UK-wide abattoir network as Critical National Infrastructure, ensuring the inclusion of abattoirs in food, farming and land use strategies as well as in national planning policy.

2 Local governments should embed abattoirs in their planning, skills, procurement and sustainability strategies, ensure provision is made for new abattoirs and work cooperatively with the sector.

3 Industry should make full use of existing funding streams available to smaller abattoirs, such as those managed by local authorities.

4 Future agricultural funding should be made accessible to smaller abattoirs. Funding for new abattoirs should also be considered, as well as further rounds of the Smaller Abattoir Fund, including replicating this in devolved nations.

5 Regulation should be reformed by adopting a risk-based, proportionate approach, including cost reductions, piloting remote inspection and carrying out a wider legislative review.

6 Administrative burdens on smaller abattoirs should be eased by streamlining reporting requirements and developing a centralised data portal.

7 Skilled worker shortages should be addressed by reviewing the slaughtering apprenticeship and taking a joined-up approach to attracting more people into the sector.

8 Industry stakeholders, including abattoirs, should maintain open dialogue with trade associations, supply chains and customers to share challenges and help identify opportunities for support.

9 Small-scale, local and traceable leather production should be revived by ensuring access to government funding, embedding leather within local and national strategies and raising public and industry awareness.

10 Producers should work proactively together to ease the logistical and administrative challenges of using small abattoirs and find local solutions in areas that lack provision.

Glossary

Deadweight sales – The sale of animals to the abattoir based on the weight and grade (quality) of the carcase after slaughter.

Direct sales – When the producer sells their products direct to customers, for example through farm shops and restaurants, box schemes, vending machines or at farmers markets.

Further processing services – For example processing meat products into sausages or burgers.

Livestock Units (LSU) – Abattoir throughput is measured by unit which equates to the following:

Animal	Number of livestock units
Adult cattle and horses	1 unit
Other cattle	0.5 units
Pigs over 100kg	0.2 units
Other pigs	0.15 units
Sheep and goats	0.1 units
Lambs, kids and piglets under 15kg	0.05 units

Liveweight sales – The sale of animals, usually at auction markets, based on the weight of the live animal ‘on the hoof’.

Official Controls – The checks and monitoring of approved meat establishments (including abattoirs) delivered by the Food Standards Agency (FSA) and conducted by Official Veterinarians and Meat Hygiene Inspectors to ensure quality control, food safety and hygiene.

Official Veterinarian (OV) – A vet who oversees and enforces animal welfare and food hygiene standards, carrying out pre and post slaughter inspections.

Over Thirty Months (OTM) – Refers to cattle that are over 30 months old at time of slaughter and therefore require extra inspection and processing due to BSE regulations (although this will change in light of the UK’s updated negligible risk status).

Private kill – A service offered by abattoirs, where producers send an animal to be slaughtered and the meat is returned to them (enabling direct selling).

Small abattoir – The Government currently defines a small abattoir as processing under 1,000 Livestock Units per annum. However, the 2024 Smaller Abattoir Fund was available for red meat abattoirs slaughtering less than 10k LSUs per annum. The Abattoir Sector Group’s proposed definition of red meat abattoir sizes is as follows:

Livestock Units per annum	Abattoir size classification
Under 1,000	Micro/low-throughput
Under 10,000	Small
Under 25,000	Medium
Above 25,000	Large

Introduction

Small abattoirs are essential for the supply of local, traceable and higher-welfare meat.¹ They provide a vital route to local markets by offering private kill (where meat is returned to the producer) and further processing services that support direct and local selling of added value products—crucial for rural economies and local meat businesses.

The existence of a diverse network of smaller operators offering a range of services is essential to the UK's food security, providing diversity in the supply chain and reducing the risks associated with large-scale, centralised and import-reliant supply chains.²

At a time when livestock farmers face challenges from the loss of the Basic Payment Scheme (particularly in the uplands and Less Favoured Areas) and continued uncertainty around the future of agricultural funding, adding value to their products is increasingly seen as fundamental to the survival of their businesses.

Meanwhile, the sustainability of livestock production is under growing scrutiny, with increasing recognition of the need to support a transition away from intensive systems, that rely heavily on energy-intensive agrochemicals and bought-in feed. In contrast, agroecological, pasture-based systems offer wide-reaching benefits—from improved soil health and biodiversity to their central role in building a more circular and resilient food system.³

Smaller abattoirs, and the services they offer, are important to the business model of these more sustainable forms of livestock production.¹ They directly support the delivery of the many public goods associated with agroecological systems. Small abattoirs process rare and native breeds, making them key to preserving genetic diversity, conserving semi-natural grassland habitats, and enabling the expansion of agroforestry and rewilding projects. A diverse network of small, local abattoirs can also support animal welfare,

for example by helping to minimise the distances animals must travel to slaughter, and by offering emergency slaughter services for injured animals.⁴

Small abattoirs play an important role in helping to meet the Government's priorities—including on economic growth, local and sustainable procurement, food security and farming profitability. Their importance is especially relevant in the context of ongoing Government strategies and reviews, including the Food Strategy, 25-Year Farming Roadmap and Land Use Framework, as well as the development of local strategies and planning policies. Infrastructure like smaller abattoirs is the foundation on which a thriving, sustainable food sector and rural economy can be built.

Closures and financial pressure

Despite the clear importance of this sector, the number of abattoirs in the UK has declined from around 2,500 in the 1970s to just 203 today.⁵ According to the AHDB, there were just 50 'small' abattoirs (those slaughtering less than 1,000 Livestock Units per annum) processing cattle and 27 processing sheep in England in 2024.⁶ Recent closures include Long Compton in the Cotswolds and McIntyre Meats in the Yorkshire Dales.

The reasons for this decline are complex, including the burden of a regulatory system that is not risk based or proportionate for the smaller sector, a lack of skilled labour and the retirement of business owners without a succession plan.¹ Financial pressure due to rising running costs such as energy prices and animal by-product

collection charges, combined with the collapse in value of hides and skins (once a significant income stream), is also driving closures. The sector has been heavily underinvested, and many small operators report making little to no profit. While the Smaller Abattoir Fund, which ran from December 2023–September 2024, was successful in giving the sector a boost, it was not enough on its own to address the ongoing financial pressures.

Small abattoir discount on meat inspection charges

Under UK regulations, all abattoirs must have a fully qualified vet present to inspect the live animal prior to slaughter, as well as the carcass after slaughter. Abattoirs are charged per hour for vet attendance, irrespective of animals slaughtered per day. When the system was introduced, a discount was incorporated to ensure the smaller premises were not unfairly disadvantaged by the charges. This discount covers up to 90% of charges for smaller abattoirs and without it many would be paying nine times more per animal than a large abattoir for the equivalent amount of hours, leading many to close down.

In October 2024, the Food Standards Agency launched a Call for Evidence on the impact of discounts on charges for official controls and other official activities in relation to meat premises.⁷ This raised concerns that the Small Abattoir Discount could be removed or reduced.

The impact of increased veterinary presence when abattoirs process more than 1,000 LSUs is why the Abattoir Sector Group (ASG)ⁱ has been lobbying for adoption of the 5% flexibility which allows smaller abattoirs to process up to 5% of the total national throughput without triggering full inspection. The process of adopting the 5% rule is currently being progressed by Government.

Following the FSA's call for evidence and follow up discussions, this survey was created to help build the evidence base for maintaining the Small Abattoir Discount. The results were shared with the FSA in April 2025 and informed the case presented to the FSA Board in June. The FSA acknowledged the importance of the small abattoir sector and the need for a form of the discount to be maintained.

Information about the survey

This survey was put together by the Sustainable Food Trust in collaboration with the Soil Association and Rare Breeds Survival Trust, and with input from others in the Abattoir Sector Group, including National Craft Butchers and Pasture for Life. It was aimed at livestock producers across the UK, particularly those sending red meat animals to slaughter, to find out more about the importance of local abattoirs for their businesses, as well as the challenges they face in accessing abattoir services.

The survey opened on Wednesday 5th March 2025 and closed on Tuesday 25th March. A full list of questions can be found in Appendix A.

This survey builds on a survey carried out by the Sustainable Food Trust and National Craft Butchers in 2022.⁸

ⁱ The Abattoir Sector Group (ASG) was set up in 2020 to provide a unified voice for the small, local abattoir sector and to advise Government. The group comprises industry, farming and animal welfare representatives.

Survey respondents

The survey received 1003 responses overall, with 850 considered complete enough for analysis. Most respondents came from England (729), followed by Wales (67), Scotland (51) and Northern Ireland (2).

87 out of 107 counties (or local authorities in the case of Scotland) were represented, including every English county besides Greater London, and all but three Welsh counties. The largest proportion of respondents came from South and Southwest England.

What type of farming systems were represented?

Survey respondents operated a range of farm enterprises. The majority produced sheep, cattle and pigs, with a smaller number producing other livestock such as poultry, goats and deer.

Farm size and stocking levels varied widely, from smallholdings sending only a few animals to slaughter each year to large enterprises managing several thousand head of livestock. Respondents' annual meat sales value ranged from 0 (for those who rear livestock for home consumption only) to more than £1 million, with 57% of respondents earning between £1000 and £100k.

44% of respondents were certified under at least one environmental or welfare scheme. The most common were Red Tractor (28%), Organic (Soil Association/OF&G) (19%) and Pasture for Life (11%). Other schemes mentioned included Quality Meat Scotland, Farm Assured Welsh Livestock, RSPCA Assured, LEAF and the Biodynamic Association.

50% of respondents were part of government Agri-Environment Schemes.

77% sent native breeds to slaughter in the last 12 months.

10% carried out conservation grazing on behalf of conservation bodies, including:

- Areas of Outstanding Natural Beauty (AONB)
- Wildlife Trusts
- Local councils
- National Trust
- Natural England
- Woodland Trust
- Forestry Commission
- RSPB
- National Parks
- Localised conservation groups, many of which were funded by the Farming in Protected Landscapes programme (FiPL)

Figure 1: Number of livestock sent to slaughter by respondents in the last 12 months*

* Cattle, sheep and pigs.
Data from Q13 and Q18

Where do respondents sell their meat?

Respondents sold their meat via multiple channels, with many using more than one route. **Around 60% sold at least some of their meat products directly to consumers**, for example through their own farm shops, vending machines, online orders and at farmers' markets (Figure 2). 40% operate their own meat box schemes (see Appendix B for a more detailed breakdown).

Only a small proportion (5%) reported selling meat to supermarkets or other large retailers.

However, 35% sold at least some animals to an abattoir or processor as deadweight, and many also sold animals live, for example as stores to be fattened. This suggests that a significantly larger proportion of respondents' meat may reach the mass market than this survey directly captures.

Just over half of respondents (56%) processed animals for home consumption or friends and family. Of these, around two thirds also sold their products through other commercial routes.

Figure 2: Where respondents sell their meat % respondents selling via each channel

Data from Q31

* Selling through at least one of: own farm shop, own butchers, vending machine, fridge/freezer, own charcuterie, own box scheme, online orders, farmers market, own catering business.

** Selling to at least one of: other farm shops, butchers, box schemes, hospitality, local procurement, catering.

Abattoir use

What type of abattoirs were used?

128 UK abattoirs were mentioned in total, the majority of which were small to medium-sized, although larger abattoirs were also mentioned (see Appendix C for a full list).

Over a third of respondents (35%) used more than one abattoir. Additional abattoirs may be used to supply different markets (for example using one abattoir for private kill and another for deadweight sales), to process different species, animals with special requirements (e.g. OTM cattle or cull sows), or to access processing services such as butchery.

What services were used?

Around 90% of respondents used abattoirs for private kill arrangements, where the carcass is returned to the producer for direct sales or home consumption.

35% used abattoirs for general deadweight sales (purchased by the abattoir to be sold on to wholesalers, butchers, caterers, etc).

Smaller abattoirs tend to offer a wide range of these additional processing services, which a significant number of people said they used (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Abattoir services used by respondents

Data from Q12 (primary abattoir only)

* e.g. sausages and burgers.

** e.g. delivery to butcher or return of horns.

Hides and skins

The collapse in value of hides and skins has had a major impact on the viability of small abattoirs. Abattoirs once received as much as £45 per hide and £6.50 per lamb skin, which was enough to cover the slaughter cost. This has now turned on its head and abattoirs pay significant amounts to have animal by-products, including hides and skins, taken away as waste.

It is believed there were around 4,000 tanneries in the UK in the early 1900s but the sector collapsed in the 1980s with the rise of China and India providing cheap manufacturing and supply chains, coupled with rising costs of more stringent effluent regulations in the UK. By 1983 there were 125 tanneries and by 2015 there were 23.⁹ Today, just a small handful of facilities are left.

Our survey found that 122 respondents (14.6%) already collect hides and/or skins to be further processed by themselves or others.

Almost half (n=392) expressed interest in collecting hides and skins if they had an option for further processing or the service of salting or shipping to a processor.

“I would really like to be able to use my hides, it would make an important contribution to our margin, make use of what is otherwise a waste or by-product, and enable other skills and businesses.”

British Pasture Leather has established the first supply chain dedicated to producing leather from the hides of cattle raised on regenerative farms in the UK. Through this work, they have developed a deep understanding of the challenges faced by smaller abattoirs – particularly around securing consistent value for hides and skins – as well as an understanding of the landscape for trading these raw materials.

In response, they have explored ways to enhance the value of hides by piloting traceability systems within smaller abattoirs, enabling farm-level information to be transferred through to the finished leather. This is increasingly relevant in the context of new EU Deforestation Regulation, rising consumer concerns around animal welfare, and the growing need for brands to account for their Tier 4 supply chain impacts.

British Pasture Leather sees significant opportunity for small, local abattoirs to improve internal traceability and strengthen supply chain relationships by fostering closer links between stakeholders in the leather supply chain and associated industries. They supported their partner abattoir in securing funding from the Smaller Abattoir Fund and will begin developing the next phase of this system in autumn 2025. In parallel, they continue to cultivate relationships with British brands and leather users who are committed to supporting the resilience and evolution of these vital systems. The business is looking to propose pilot projects which seek to establish new and secure markets for hides and skins from small, local abattoirs.

Distance to slaughter

How far did respondents travel?

While distance to slaughter is only one of several issues affecting welfare during live animal transport, the Government has adopted the principle that distance to slaughter should be minimised.⁴ Many farmers cite animal welfare through shorter and less stressful journeys to slaughter as one of the benefits of a network of small, local abattoirs. When asked to rank the benefits of local abattoirs in the 2022 NCB-SFT Abattoir Users Survey, animal welfare came out top.⁸ However, as abattoirs continue to close, animals are being taken on increasingly long journeys to slaughter, while some farmers are having to give up altogether due to rising costs of travel and welfare concerns.

Despite this, nearly 60% of respondents to this survey travelled less than 30 miles to reach their abattoir. Across England, Wales and the UK overall, the average distance fell within the 31–40 mile range, with typical journey times between 30 minutes and one hour. While this is close to ideal in terms of both welfare and financial viability, it

remains fragile given the ongoing threat of future abattoir closures. In Scotland however, travel distances varied much more widely, with the average falling into the 61–70 mile bracket.

When asked how far their next nearest suitable abattoir would be, the distances reported by respondents were more variable, with the UK average rising from 31–40 to 41–50 miles.

Some respondents travelled extremely long distances to slaughter. For example, 10 respondents in England and 14 in Scotland said they travel more than 100 miles to slaughter, with the longest journey taking between 6.5 and 8 hours (from Orkney to Dingwall). Reasons for longer journey distances and times include travel via ferries for island farmers, abattoir closures or loss of services necessitating longer journeys to the next nearest suitable abattoir, and difficult rural roads and traffic. Some respondents chose not to use their nearest abattoir because it does not offer the services they need, requiring them to travel further distances. It should also be noted that the majority of respondents were currently using a small abattoir, and therefore results may not fully reflect the number of people who have gone out of business due to increased distances.

Figure 4: Journey time to primary abattoir

Data from Q22

Figure 5: Distance to primary abattoir

Data from Q21

“Animal welfare has been reduced due to the local abattoir being closed. The animals now endure over a day’s travel, including time in market, against under an hour’s travel they used to have.”

Figure 6: Distance to next suitable abattoir

Data from Q21

* e.g. unsure how far, or wouldn’t consider using the next nearest

Access to abattoir services

Two thirds of survey respondents reported facing issues in accessing appropriate abattoir services in the last 5 years, **with one third having seen the abattoir they had been using shut down.**

13 abattoirs which have already closed were mentioned. Notably, 26 people had been using Newmans, which closed in January 2025, while 15 had been using Long Compton, which closed in 2024. Other recently closed abattoirs that were mentioned included Mettricks, Tideford, Tottingworth, McIntyre Meats and Cig Calon Cymru. Since this survey closed, there has been a further closure, this time of a large abattoir – Scotbeef in Inverurie, Scotland.

Besides closure, the most common problem identified by respondents was related to **the abattoir being too busy or fully booked (24%)**. This indicates the pressure placed on remaining abattoirs, many of which are operating at maximum capacity. As a result, many smaller abattoirs have stopped offering important services, such as private kill, cutting, packing and further processing. Some have also stopped doing multi-species slaughter.

Among certified organic respondents (n=148), the most commonly reported issue was difficulty accessing an organic abattoir, affecting 40% of this group.

“ [Our] local abattoir is becoming increasingly busy as others are now shut. We have to book well in advance, in some cases up to a year in advance, which is quite tricky to judge customer demand and the number of animals needed.”

Figure 7: Reasons for issues accessing abattoir services

“ Abattoir recently changed policy to no horned cattle. This has been devastating for our business. Now having to travel 71 miles and cost has nearly doubled.”

Data from Q24

* Cattle over 30 months. ** e.g. religious slaughter, unsatisfied with service quality

Lilliput Farm Kitchen is the first restaurant in England to be certified by Pasture for Life, a certification that goes beyond ‘grass-fed’, to guarantee all beef sold comes from animals raised on 100% grass and forage, with no grain or soya. Customers travel from Bath, Bristol and London to eat beef from animals they can often see grazing just outside the restaurant.

Key Facts

- 68 ha organic pasture
- 68-head Traditional Hereford herd
- 100% pasture-fed: no grain or soya
- £60.40 average transaction
- 21,744 customers in first year
- 14 staff across farm, kitchen and front of house
- Events venue for weddings and corporate gatherings

Beef production and butchery

The farm’s Traditional Hereford cattle herd live outdoors, are weaned at 11 months, and are pasture-fed to full maturity at three years. All animals are slaughtered at H.F. Stiles & Son, a small abattoir in Bromham, then dry-aged and butchered on-site.

This full control allows for low-waste, high-welfare cooking. Head Chef Debbie Nicholls and Sous Chef Liam Bradley use the whole animal across seasonal menus and frozen retail packs.

Public demand and education

Many guests say it’s the first time they’ve knowingly eaten truly pasture-fed beef. The team explain how the animals are raised and why it matters, from soil health to animal welfare, building long-term customer trust and support.

Commercial model and risk

By selling beef direct, Lilliput adds over £1,000 of value per animal, earning £3,200 per carcass: a 50% uplift on typical market returns. However, this depends on accessing a local abattoir, a skilled on-site butcher, and a customer base that values ethical food.

The farm has been organically certified for 21 years and part of Countryside Stewardship for 26. However, uncertainty in government funding, including a pause on the Sustainable Farming Incentive (SFI), threaten the future of farms like this.

The role of the local abattoir

Without a local abattoir, Lilliput’s business model would break down, as the beef could not be processed or sold on-site. A working, profitable, transparent alternative to industrial meat would disappear.

“ We’re proving this kind of farming works, but only because the public are given a choice. Without small abattoirs and proper support, that choice disappears.”

Aidan Stanley, Co-founder

How does access to an abattoir impact farming and meat businesses?

Existing challenges with accessing appropriate abattoir services has affected respondents’ businesses in various ways, with two thirds reporting some form of negative impact.

For many respondents, selling their products locally through short supply chains was central to their business model: **58%** believed their business would not be profitable without selling direct to consumers or through local markets.

However, the lack of services such as private kill and further processing has limited the ability to add value through direct or local sales. This has led some respondents to sell to the mass market rather than processing livestock for direct or local sale:

18% reported having to send livestock to market.

15% have had to use a large processor instead of a local abattoir.

Opportunities to expand and diversify have also been affected due to lack of access to abattoir services:

- **17%** have not been able to expand their business.
- **11%** have not been able to diversify their business.
- **14%** have reduced the number of livestock they keep.

Almost a fifth of organically certified respondents (**19%**) said they have had to stop selling their meat as organic due to lack of access to organic abattoir services.

On the extreme end of the spectrum, 7 respondents have had to close their meat business.

“The lack of reliable abattoir services has meant that we cannot be confident that we can provide a regular supply of meat to meet the needs of our customers, limiting our ability to expand our business and rely on this outlet for our meat more.”

What would be the impact of further closures?

Further abattoir closures or loss of key services would have even more severe consequences.

Almost **90%** of respondents said they would be negatively impacted if their local abattoir were to close. Only **2%** said they would see no impact.

43% said they would not be able to sell their meat locally, while **29%** may have to close their meat business altogether (Figure 8).

Almost a third would send their animals to market and a quarter would sell to a large processor instead of selling locally.

Other key concerns raised include the animal welfare concerns and costs associated with travelling further to the next nearest abattoir. Many also said their next nearest abattoir does not offer the services they need.

“The extra time/distance/cost would reduce margins. We may stop selling beef and raising native breeds and change to commercial stores instead or reduce numbers.”

Figure 8: 'If your local abattoir were to close, what would be the impact on your business?'

Data from Q27

What would better access to abattoir services mean?

Respondents were asked how better access to abattoir services would impact their business. Responses highlighted the positive impact this could have on farm businesses:

27% of respondents said they could sell direct or through local markets, while **18%** would consider opening a meat retail business.

26% said they could expand their business and **17%** could diversify their business.

Around 100 survey respondents expressed interest in being involved with or supporting **the creation of a new abattoir**. However, many were concerned about the cost barriers, time and skills required. There was significant interest in setting up abattoirs which are cooperatively owned and run, including mobile slaughter units.

“It would give me more confidence to build further markets.”

“An efficient local abattoir, specialising in native breeds would simplify this aspect of our business, saving money and time which would heighten the likelihood if us expanding. It would also be a major improvement in animal welfare.”

“I could sell or utilise more of each animal.”

The cost of slaughter

Respondents were asked about the amount abattoirs charge and the impact of increased charges. Many abattoirs report little to no profit in slaughtering, especially private kill, and with the rise in costs of running a small business, including energy and fuel, equipment, waste collection, staff costs and FSA charges, there is often a need to increase charges to customers. However, this understandably impacts the farmer and, ultimately, the consumer.

60% of respondents have seen the cost of slaughter increase in the past 12 months. **16%** saw no change, **6%** saw decreased charges and **17%** responded as unsure/not applicable. In their comments, respondents described annual slaughter charge increases ranging between **3%** and **41%**, and roughly **16%** on average.

When asked about the impact of increased slaughter charges, and the potential impact of a further **10%** increase, respondents expressed serious concern.

One summarised the key dilemma:

“The price of the finished product would either have to increase to reflect this, which is likely to reduce sales, or we would have to absorb the increased cost to lessen the impact on sales.”

Many respondents described facing this difficult choice in their comments:

- One third (n=199) said they would pass either part of or the full cost onto their customers or the supply chain.
- One quarter (n=159) said they would be likely to absorb the cost, reducing often already tight profit margins.

11% of respondents (n=70) said they would seriously question the overall viability of their business and consider closing their operation.

Many respondents worried that further increases would make their products unaffordable, especially compared to supermarket alternatives – despite strong interest in provenance and local sourcing.

However, there was a general understanding that abattoirs need to increase prices to stay in business and several said that they would rather bear the cost or pass it on to customers than see their local abattoir close, compromising the availability of local meat altogether.

“Charges have increased which is difficult but I am very grateful that I have a local abattoir that is organically certified, so I am ‘happy’ to pay more to keep the abattoir going.”

Aside from slaughter charges, increased hanging, cutting, butchery, deboning, packing and haulage costs were also mentioned. Coupled with rising costs in other areas, such as feed and fuel, and in some cases the loss of income from Government schemes, respondents frequently reinforced the challenge in maintaining a viable business.

Beyond concerns around price and profitability, many respondents indicated that rising charges either had already led – or were likely to lead – to changes in their business models. Moving away from local or direct sales, reducing livestock numbers, or selling animals at market were mentioned most frequently. Those processing livestock for personal consumption were less affected, though some noted it could become too expensive or uneconomical over time.

This is important when considering the future of the FSA's Small Abattoir Discount and any further increase to inspection charges. In 2025, there has already been an increase of **17.7%** for the hourly rate of OVs and an **11.3%** increase for the hourly rate of Meat Hygiene Inspectors.

“We are getting squeezed at every turn. Higher feed costs, higher transport costs, higher abattoir costs, a general public who are also counting their finances and no support from the government.”

“Sheep kill price has doubled in the last two years for us. Cattle and pig costs have risen too. It all erodes margin and profitability and the sustainability of a local production and consumption model.”

Demand for local meat

Access to locally produced, high-welfare meat is increasingly valued by consumers seeking sustainable, traceable food. For example, the 2025 Organic Market Report survey found that organic sales through independent retail rose by **9%** in 2024, a rise largely attributed to growing consumer concerns around health and sustainability.¹⁰ While cost-of-living pressures remain a key barrier – highlighted by an Eating Better survey in which two thirds (**67%**) of respondents said meat produced to higher standards was too expensive¹¹ – the average farmgate premium for organic products is **27%**, compared with a **70%** average premium in supermarkets.¹⁰ This demonstrates the positive role of short supply chains, and the importance of ensuring farm retailers are not forced to increase prices unnecessarily due to challenges with slaughter and butchery.

61% of respondents said they have seen increased demand for their meat products in recent years.

However, many respondents described challenges in meeting this demand.

When asked about changes to their meat sales, only **21%** said these had increased in recent years, mostly attributed to business expansion, diversification into direct sales and value-added products.

12% had seen a decrease in sales, most commonly due to abattoir closures or reduced services, a drop in livestock numbers or the need to raise prices, making products less accessible or desirable to consumers.

“Margins are tight for private sales after kill and butchery costs – at the moment our customers are bearing these extra costs but we have lost some sales recently, so it may push us out of cattle or into stores in the future.”

Employment

Livestock production supports rural employment, particularly in more remote or economically disadvantaged areas. Agroecological producers and farm retailers are especially well placed to offer a diverse range of skilled, meaningful jobs across farming, education, agritourism, processing and retail.

Respondents and their meat businesses represented a total of 2,020 jobs. While 86% employ up to 3 people, some reported as many as 100 employees.

15 respondents have already had to reduce the number of people they employ or cut their hours due to issues accessing an abattoir.

53 respondents said that they could employ more people if they had better access to an abattoir.

Aside from their own business, respondents highlighted the knock-on effect that their local abattoir closing could have for their employees and others in the supply chain that rely on their business:

“It would be catastrophic for our business and put our employment of 17+ people at serious risk.”

“...it’s unlikely [an alternative local abattoir] could take on all the work undertaken by the abattoir we use. As a result, we are likely to get less contract butchery work to do, which would mean reduced hours for our butchery staff and the financial viability of our on-farm butchery would be questionable.”

Case Study

Essington Farm Shop, Wolverhampton

Based just outside Wolverhampton, Essington Farm Shop has been retailing quality home-grown produce since 1892. The award-winning butchery and deli are central to the business, accounting for over half of its annual turnover – with the butchery generating £1.8 million and the deli £450,000.

The butchery processes approximately 4–5 bodies of beef, 25 pigs, 15 lambs and 75 cases of chicken each week. This includes pigs and cattle reared on the farm, alongside livestock from neighbouring farms, all of which are slaughtered at the local abattoir.

Employment

The business employs 70 staff across the farm shop, butchery, deli, restaurant and farm, including:

- 9 full-time butchers
- 1 part-time butcher
- 1 apprentice
- 9 counter assistants

Sales

Analysis of recent sales data shows:

- A 10% increase in butchery sales volume year-on-year.
- An 8% increase in customers purchasing from the butchery, with nearly 7000 customers buying meat products in March 2025.
- An average spend of £22 on butchery items, accounting for 80 – 90% of average basket value.

Customer feedback

Insights from the loyalty card scheme and direct correspondence reveal:

- An increase in customers concerned about the way their meat is produced, particularly in relation to animal welfare, environmental impact and health.

- A younger demographic seeking high welfare, quality local meat.
- Greater demand for traditional counter service by a butcher, driven by a trend towards home cooking, especially BBQ, and most supermarkets offering only pre-packed meat.

Access to a viable local abattoir is fundamental to the continuing success of Essington Farm’s retail operations. Without it, the business would lose the ability to serve the market for high welfare, local meat, risking the loss of £2.25m worth of sales, over 20 redundancies and leaving a major gap in the market.

Provision of public goods

Challenges accessing appropriate abattoir services are undermining the ability of livestock farmers to operate more sustainable systems and deliver key public goods. The survey findings demonstrate how limited abattoir availability, especially private kill, OTM and organic services, along with increased costs and distance to slaughter, risk reducing profitability, restricting sales options and limiting opportunities for on-farm diversification.

Many of the respondents in this survey operate high-welfare, agroecological livestock systems, with **20%** organic and **11%** Pasture for Life certified, more than three quarters rearing rare and native breeds and half receiving government money for agri-environment schemes.

In total, **83% of respondents believed livestock were important for the delivery of public goods on their farm.**

Some of the public goods mentioned included:

- Conservation grazing for species-rich habitats including wetlands, woodlands, grasslands, uplands, chalk downland, floodplains, wildflower meadows and heathlands
- Soil health and carbon sequestration
- Natural pest and weed management
- Maintenance of hedgerows and biodiversity corridors
- Rewilding and agroforestry
- Public education and wellbeing, including school visits and interaction with livestock

“[Livestock] are absolutely vital to graze and manage our wildflower meadows and the fertility-building phase of our organic rotation.”

“Ground nesting birds such as curlew, lapwings and oystercatchers rely on the suckler herd and followers to provide plenty of insect life to raise their broods of chicks.”

Some farmers cited the lack of suitable abattoirs as a key barrier to becoming certified – despite already managing land and livestock to high standards. This hinders producers’ ability to communicate the wider benefits of their production systems to consumers, and may prevent them from receiving a price premium for their meat products.

“Part of the land is certified organic, but not the livestock. If we were in a position to sell direct, we’d go for Pasture for Life for our lamb.”

“I haven’t become organic as I can’t get my animals killed through an organic abattoir.”

Implications for native breeds – The Rare Breeds Survival Trust

The findings of this survey bring home the significant threat to the viability of native breeds in the UK resulting from the declining availability of local abattoirs.

Among respondents, 24 native cattle breeds, 45 sheep and 12 pig breeds were represented, including 11 ‘Priority’ and 26 ‘At risk’ breeds, as classified by the Rare Breeds Survival Trust (see Appendix D).

Many farmers using rare and native breeds rely on small, local facilities capable of taking small numbers of different species and breeds to maintain high welfare and low-stress slaughter, direct sales, and short supply chains. Without this infrastructure, producers are forced to adapt to more centralised and commercialised routes to market, which often favour faster-growing, intensively farmed breeds.

A concerning **17% of respondents reported that they would no longer be able to keep native breeds if their local abattoir were to close.** This reflects the fragility of native breed systems, which are often small-scale, low-input, and tailored to specific environments and markets. Larger, more distant abattoirs frequently lack the flexibility or willingness to accommodate smaller batches, diverse carcass specifications or on-farm slaughter requirements. This puts disproportionate pressure on native breed farmers to change their systems or exit them entirely.

More than three quarters of survey respondents rear rare and native breeds, and **50%** participate in agri-environment schemes which recognise the environmental value of these animals. Their role in maintaining species-rich grasslands, sequestering carbon, and supporting biodiversity is well documented. Native livestock are often better suited to unimproved or marginal land, thriving in extensive, pasture-based systems that deliver both environmental and public goods.

However, pressures on the abattoir network risk undermining these benefits. Faced with fewer local slaughter options, higher transport costs, and reduced ability to market premium, provenance-led meat, some producers may feel forced to switch to more intensive systems using commercial breeds to remain viable. This would represent not only a loss of genetic heritage but a step backwards in terms of farm sustainability and the development of local, resilient food systems.

If native breeds are to continue playing a key role in agroecological farming, dedicated support for local abattoirs is essential.

“We use our Belted Galloways to graze areas of ancient chalk grassland on our farm. They play a huge part in the restoration of these very important habitats.”

“I have had to reduce the provision of conservation grazing due to lack of abattoir capacity & OTM provision.”

Conclusions

The overall trend of closures in the small abattoir sector remains alarming. The findings of this survey demonstrate the serious impact that a lack of suitable abattoir services has on farming businesses and local meat supply chains.

The findings also show how important small and local abattoir services are to many farmers, with them being seen as playing a key role in supporting:

- Stronger, more resilient local meat supply chains, supporting national food security and helping to satisfy consumers' increasing interest in meat provenance and sustainability.
- Rural economic growth, supporting farming businesses and jobs in livestock husbandry, slaughter, butchery, retail and agritourism.
- Public goods delivery, by improving the viability of farmers already practising, or shifting towards sustainable livestock production.
- Conservation of rare and native breeds which are important for genetic diversity and semi-natural habitat management, including rewilding projects.
- Improved animal welfare, for example through enabling reduced journey times to slaughter and supporting high-welfare farming systems.

Much work has been, and continues to be, done to address the challenges facing the sector – particularly through the Abattoir Sector Group, Defra's Small Abattoir Working Group and the Small Abattoir Task and Finish Group – co-chaired by Defra and the ASG. The willingness of Defra to engage with the sector has resulted in positive progress.

Progress achieved to date includes:

- **Smaller Abattoir Fund in England (2024):** 42% of eligible abattoirs applied for capital grants to improve productivity, add value to primary products, enhance animal health and welfare or invest in innovation and new technology.
- **Negligible BSE Risk Status:** Following lobbying from the sector, the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH) downgraded the UK's risk status for BSE. The abattoir and meat processing industry will be able to take advantage of changes to control measures, which will reduce operational burden and release financial savings.
- **5% rule:** Defra is progressing the adoption of this EU flexibility that would allow eligible abattoirs that process up to 5% of the national throughput to operate without requiring full inspection and charges.
- **Slaughter apprenticeship review:** Efforts are underway to review the slaughtering apprenticeship, with proposals put forward from industry for an apprenticeship that better aligns with the needs of smaller abattoirs.
- **Animal by-products:** Ideas are being explored and piloted to improve the collection and processing of by-products, particularly hides and skins.

However, more work is needed to address the challenges at every level.

Recommendations

The following recommendations should be considered as part of a wider '**National Plan for Local Meat**'.

1 National Government should formally recognise the UK-wide abattoir network as Critical National Infrastructure (CNI).

While the food sector as a whole is already designated as CNI, Government should make an explicit commitment to the role that a diverse network of abattoirs – offering the right services in the right places – plays in supporting farming viability, food security, animal welfare, environmental land management, rural employment and economic growth.

Government must ensure small abattoirs are included in relevant food, farming and land use strategies, such as the Farming Roadmap, Food Strategy, Land Use Framework and national planning policy.

2 Local governments should embed local food infrastructure, including abattoirs, in their planning, skills, procurement and sustainability strategies.

Where a small abattoir closes, local authorities must ensure a new site is identified and planning approval is expedited. They should also work cooperatively with farming groups and local meat businesses to ensure appropriate abattoir services are being provided for the area.

3 Industry should make full use of existing funding streams available to smaller abattoirs, such as those managed by local authorities.

Existing funding opportunities need to be better communicated to the sector.

4 Further Government funding should be considered.

Smaller abattoirs should be included in relevant future agricultural funding.

Learnings can be made from the previous Smaller Abattoir Fund to enable a more targeted future fund that could deliver further significant benefit, particularly if funding for new abattoirs was also made available. Replicating this fund in devolved nations should also be considered.

5 Reform regulation and adopt a risk-based, proportionate approach.

This includes identifying where cost savings can be made within the current regulatory and inspection regime as identified by industry groups. The use of remote inspection technologies should be piloted to reduce burdens without compromising welfare.

A wider legislative review is needed to deliver fit-for-purpose regulation for smaller abattoirs, to include comparison with other EU models and ways of implementing regulation.

6 Ease the administrative burden.

Ways to reduce the paperwork and administrative burden on abattoirs should be sought, through streamlining processes and centralising data.

7 Address skilled worker shortages in the slaughtering and meat processing sector.

A slaughtering apprenticeship review should be fully supported by government to enable more flexibility for those wishing to train in slaughtering and butchery. The funding level for this apprenticeship needs to be high enough to ensure viability.

A joined-up approach is needed for recruitment, including working with the Department for Education to embed the importance of this sector within education and careers advice.

8 Industry stakeholders, including abattoirs, should maintain open dialogue with their trade associations, supply chains and customers.

This would help to share challenges and identify opportunities for support. Improved communication can aid collective problem-solving and help reduce the risk of further closures.

9 Support the revival of small-scale, local and traceable leather production.

For example by improving access to government funding and incorporating leather production in national and local government strategic planning in relation to small abattoirs, local supply chains, economic growth and sustainability. Greater public and industry awareness is also needed to drive demand and enable expansion of production.

10 Producers should work proactively together.

Producers can coordinate to improve administrative processes, bookings, ensure predictable throughput and share transport and meat collection. This model is being piloted successfully in Scotland via a government-funded 'Private Kill Coordinator'.

In areas lacking abattoir provision, farmer groups should explore collaborative solutions, such as assessing the feasibility of setting up a new abattoir or taking over one that is closing. Maintaining open communication with local abattoirs about their future is essential to long-term planning.

The Sustainable Food Trust, Soil Association and Rare Breeds Survival Trust will continue to advocate for small abattoirs, both through the work of our own organisations and collectively as members of the Abattoir Sector Group.

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Appendices

Appendix A: Survey questions

-
- Q1** Please tell us the location of your business
-
- Q2** Please select your county/local authority (Scotland)
-
- Q3** Please enter your postcode
-
- Q4** What type of farm business do you operate? Tick all that apply.
-
- Q5** How many livestock do you keep? Please enter approximate numbers for those which apply
-
- Q6** What is the total number of people employed as part of your meat business?
-
- Q7** Are you certified within any schemes? Please select all that apply
-
- Q8** Are livestock important for the delivery of public goods on your farm?
-
- Q9** Are you part of any agri–environment schemes?
-
- Q10** Do you employ conservation grazing on behalf of conservation organisations?
-
- Q11** Which abattoir do you send most of your livestock to?
-
- Q12** Which services do you use at this abattoir?
-
- Q13** Approximately how many of each type of livestock have you sent to this abattoir in the past 12 months?
-
- Q14** Were any of the above native breeds?
-
- Q15** Do you use more than one abattoir?
-
- Q16** Which other abattoir do you use?
-
- Q17** Which services do you use at this additional abattoir? Tick all that apply.
-
- Q18** Approximately how many of the following have you sent to this abattoir in the past 12 months?
-
- Q19** Were any of the above native breeds?
-
- Q20** Do you collect hides and/or skins to have them further processed?
-
- Q21** How far do you travel to take animals to slaughter?
-
- Q22** How long does this journey take on average?
-
- Q23** Do you know how far your next nearest suitable abattoir would be?
-
- Q24** Have you had any issues accessing an abattoir in the last 5 years?
Please select the reasons or tick 'no issues' below
-
- Q25** How has the lack of access to an appropriate abattoir impacted your business if at all? Please select all that apply or select 'no impact' below
-

Q26 If you do not currently have access to suitable abattoir services, how would it impact your business if you did? Please select all that apply.

Q27 If your current local abattoir were to close, what would be the impact on your business? Please select all that apply or select 'no impact'

Q28 Have you seen a significant change to abattoir charges over the last 12 months?

Q29 If abattoir charges were to significantly increase (by 10% or more) what impact would that have on your business?

Q30 Do you have access to a livestock market? If so, which one?

Q31 Where do you sell your meat products? Please select all that apply.

Q32 What is the total annual sales value of the meat that you sell? Has this increased or decreased compared to previous years and if so, why?

Q33 Have you seen any change in demand for your meat products in recent years?

Q34 Would your business still be profitable without direct/local sales?

Q35 Are you interested in the process of setting up your own abattoir?

Q36 Do you have any further comments you would like to share?

Appendix B: Meat sales

Where respondents sell their meat

Data from Q31. Participants could choose multiple responses.
* e.g. local food hubs, cooperatives, deadweight sales only.

Appendix C: List of abattoirs used by respondents

Abattoir name	No. of respondents
England	
A C Hopkins, Taunton	1
A D Harveys, Norfolk	1
A H Griffiths, Leintwardine	14
A Wright & Son, Boston	5
ABP Ellesmere	2
ABP Frome	1
ABP Guildford	5
ABP Langport	2
ABP Sturminster	8
ABP Yetminster	6
Aireys, Grange-over-Sands	15
Alec Jarret, Bristol	6
Arthur Howell, Wells-next-the-Sea	3
Black Brow, Wigton	1
Blacklidges, Wigan	1
C Humphreys & Sons, Chelmsford	13
C E Partridge & Son, Bromsgrove	4
C J Byford and Son, Clacton-on-Sea	1
C Snell, Chard	23
C&K Meats, Eye	2
C&S Meats, Sherbourne	29
Combe Martin Meats, Ilfracombe	9
Cornish Farmhouse Bacon	3
Deer and Dexter, Penrith	1
Denney's, Kendal	19
Dovecote Park, Pontefract	8
Downland Traditional Meats, Henfield	129
Dunbia, Cardington	2
Dunbia, Carnaby	2
Dunbia, Hatherleigh West Devon	5
E & T Jackson and Sons, Knutford	4
E V Slack and Sons, Wadworth	2
East Hill Pride, Ottery St Mary	9
Edge and Son, Wirral	2
Euro Quality Lambs, Craven Arms	3
Evans and Son, Marston Moretaine	17
F Drury and Sons, Swindon	6
Farmers Fresh, Kennilworth	10
Forge Farm Meats, Southborough	16
Fosse Meadows, Lutterworth	2
Fowler Brothers, Essex	7
Foyle Food Group, Cinderford	10
G & GB Hewitt, Chester	4
Gages Farm, Ashburton	25
H Dawson and Sons, Boston	2
H F Stiles & Son, Chippenham	27
H J Hellet & Sons Kimbolton	3
H R Jasper & Sons, Launceston	3
HG Blakes, Norwich	18
HP Westwood, Walsall	3
J A Jewitt, Spennymoor	5
J A Mounfield & Son, Selby	7
J and E Medcalf, Halifax	5
J Broomhall, Stonehouse	40
J R Farm Meats, Canterbury	11
J S Quality Meats, Uttoxeter	14

J V Richards, Truro	2	T & H Lobb, Bodmin	14
J&J Farmers, Holsworthy	10	T G Sargeant & Sons, Uttoxeter	10
John Penny and Sons, Leeds	11	T M Allman, Edenbridge	9
Joseph Morris, Lutterworth	14	Thompson Wholesale Meat, Witton-le-Wear	16
Ken Ballard, Marden	8	Vivan Olds, St Just	5
Kepak, Bodmin	5	W S Clarke & Sons, Salisbury	1
L Brown and Sons, Lincoln	9	Westcountry Premium Venison, Launceston	2
L Wood and Sons, Huddersfield	1	William Taylor & Son, Preston	14
Langford, Bristol	7	Woodhead Brothers (Neerock, Morrisons Supermarket)	7
Langthornes Buffalo, Northallerton	3	Woolley Brothers, Sheffield	3
Leech and Sons, Royston	4	Wooton Organic, Daylesford	1
M C Kelly, Devon	1		
Melton Meat, Melton Mowbray	2		
Minsterworth, Gloucester	2		
Muchmeats, Witney	9		
N Bramall and Son, Sheffield	1		
Oaks Poultry Farm, Ditchling	1		
Otter Valley Poultry, Honiton	3		
P J Hayman and Sons, Ottery-St-Mary	6		
P J King and Sons, Gloucester	22		
Pickstock, Telford	7		
Pilgrims, Bristol	2		
R B Elliot and Son Chesterfield	13		
R J Trevarthen, Roskrow, Cornwall	11		
Redeferns Buxton	8		
Riley Foods Ltd, Lancashire	1		
Robert G Tuckey, Birmingham	6		
Simpson & Sons, Redditch	1		
Stillmans, Taunton	15		
Strap Orchard, Wincanton	5		
Sutton Bonnington, Nottingham	6		

Wales

Cig Eryri, Blaenau Ffestiniog	8
Cig Oen Caron, Tregaron	7
D & J Thomas, Wrexham	20
Euro Farm Foods, Haverfordwest	1
G R Evans, Corwen	3
Kepak, Meyrthyr Tydfil	8
Maddock Kembery Meats, Maesteg	14
N S James, Raglan	11
Pembrokeshire Meat Company, Haverfordwest	1
Pilgrims, Llanidloes (was Randall Parker)	3
W J George, Talgarth	8

Northern Ireland

William Grant & Co, Londonderry	2
---------------------------------	---

Scotland

ABP Perth	2
AK Stoddart, Ayrshire	3
Border Meats, Lockerbie	5
James Chapman, Shotts	5
John Scotts, Paisley	6
McIntosh Donald, Aberdeen	1
Millers of Speyside	5
Mull Slaughterhouse, Isle of Mull	1
Munro's, Dingwall	17
Scotbeef Ltd, Stirling	1
Scotbeef Inverurie	4
Stornoway, Isle of Lewis	1
West Scottish Lamb, Carlsile	1
Wishaw	8

Appendix D: Native breeds kept by respondents

Cattle	Sheep	Pigs	Other
Aberdeen Angus	Badger Face	Berkshires	Anglo Nubian Goats
Ancient Cattle of Wales	Balwen Sheep	British Lop	English Goat
Belted Galloway	Black Welsh Mountain	Glocester Old Spot	Red Deer
Blue Grey	Bluefaced Leicester	Landrace	
Dairy Shorthorn	Border Leicester	Large White	
Dexter	Borerary	Mangalitza Pigs	
English Longhorn	Brecknock Cheviots	Middle White	
Guernsey	Castlemilk Moorit	Oxford Sandy and Black	
Hereford	Clun Forest	Pietrain	
Highland	Cornwall Long Wool	Saddleback	
Irish Moiled	Cotswold Sheep	Tamworth	
Jersey	Derbyshire Gritstone	Welsh Pedigree Pigs	
Lincoln Red Cattle	Dorset Down		
Luing	Dorset Horn		
Murray Grey	Easycare		
North Devon / Ruby Red	Greyface Dartmoor		
Red Poll	Hampshire Down		
Riggitt Galloway	Hebridean		
Shetland	Herdwick		
Shorthorn	Hill Radnor		
Sussex	Icelandic Sheep		
Welsh Black	Jacobs		
White Park	Kerry Hill		
Whitebred Shorthorn	Lincoln Longwool		
	Llanwenog		
	Lleyn		
	Manx Loaghtan		
	Norfolk Horn		

Cattle	Sheep	Pigs	Other
	North Country Cheviot		
	North Ronaldsay		
	Oxford Down		
	Polled Dorset Sheep		
	Portland		
	Romney		
	Ryelands		
	Scottish Blackface		
	Shetland		
	Soay		
	South Country Cheviot		
	Suffolk		
	Teeswaters		
	Texel		
	Welsh Mountain		
	Wensleydale		
	Whitefaced Woodland		
	Wiltshire Horn		

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